

Harnessing deep learning algorithms to predict software refactoring

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ABSTRACT

During software maintenance, software systems need to be modified by adding or modifying source code. These changes are required to fix errors or adopt new requirements raised by stakeholders or market place. Identifying the targeted piece of code for refactoring purposes is considered a real challenge for software developers. The whole process of refactoring mainly relies on software developers' skills and intuition. In this paper, a deep learning algorithm is used to develop a refactoring prediction model for highlighting the classes that require refactoring. More specifically, the gated recurrent unit algorithm is used with proposed pre-processing steps for refactoring prediction at the class level. The effectiveness of the proposed model is evaluated using a very common dataset of 7 open source java projects. The experiments are conducted before and after balancing the dataset to investigate the influence of data sampling on the performance of the prediction model. The experimental analysis reveals a promising result in the field of code refactoring prediction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Software applications are endlessly maintained and modify to add new requirements, fix errors, or adapt new modules. Requirements continuously change as the market place is susceptible to stakeholders' demands. Therefore, software applications should be evolved continuously to make sure the stakeholders are satisfied. During software maintenance, programmers are asked to add a new feature, remove and/or modify existing ones. The process of adapting these features needs to modify the software systems to meet the required requirement, this process called refactoring [1]. Code refactoring plays an important role in enhancing software quality by evolving the internal structure without affecting the intended behavior [2].

Extensive research has been conducted for addressing the relationship between refactoring software systems and the quality measurements [3-10]. All experimental results show how refactoring has a direct influence on improving software quality. Therefore, predicting refactoring promptly should be investigating, and building an accurate model becomes mandatory. Software developers still face a real challenge to pick the right time and software code for refactoring purposes as the operation needs time and budget [11]. Therefore, developers should be sure about which piece of code should be evolved before starting the process of refactoring to adopt the new requirements. Although developer experience shapes the most successful factor

in this process, still prediction algorithms might be a helpful tool in this matter. These algorithms can provide the developers with some insights about which part of code should be refactored and when.

Different methodologies are designed and built to help developers in the refactoring process such as code smells detection strategies [12], logic meta-programming [13], invariant mining [14] and search-based [15, 16]. Moreover, machine learning is harnessed in the area of prediction and shows noticeable performance in terms of prediction in various fields as computer vision, defect prediction, natural language processing, code comprehension, bioinformatics, speech recognition, and finance [17-24]. Several machine learning algorithms are utilized in code refactoring prediction at class and method level as well [25, 26].

The main contribution of this work is investigating the effectiveness of deep learning algorithms in building refactoring prediction models at the class-level. The implemented deep learning algorithm is gated recurrent unit (GRU). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm is used for the first time for refactoring prediction at the class level. In this work 7 open-source Java-based projects are used to assess the effectiveness of the studied algorithm.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several attempts in the literature to use machine learning to predict and suggest refactoring. Amal *et al.* [27] used search-based software engineering for software refactoring. They used an artificial neural network (ANN) and genetic algorithms (GA) to choose between refactoring solutions. They used the opinion of 16 different software engineers to manually evaluate the refactoring solutions for training. They developed a predictive model to evaluate the refactoring solutions for the remaining iterations. The approach outperformed the manual refactoring approach. Kumar *et al.* [28] used 25 source code metrics at the method level to predict the need for refactoring. They used a publicly available dataset of five open-sourced software systems to investigate the performance of ten different machine learning classifiers. They used three different data sampling methods to tackle the unbalanced data issues.

Al Dallal [29] discussed a measure and a model to predict whether the method(s) in a class needing move method refactoring and achieved a prediction accuracy of more than 90%. The author built the predictive model over seven object-oriented systems. Aniche *et al.* [30] investigated the effectiveness of six different machine learning algorithms (logistic regression, naive Bayes, support vector machine, decision trees, random forest, and neural network) in predicting software refactoring. They used a dataset consists of over two million refactorings from 11,149 real-world projects. Pantiuchina *et al.* [31] proposed an approach to prevent instead of fix code quality issues that predict code smells. The approach uses source code quality to predict whether a module is likely to be affected by code smells in the future. The topic at hand is still in its infancy. Several advances can be made to predict code smells and refactoring opportunities that would eventually improve software quality and maintenance.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents the proposed approach for Software refactoring prediction. The proposed approach is divided into two main stages. The first stage performs a set of necessary pre-processing procedures on datasets. In the second stage, the deep learning algorithm is applied to the datasets to predict the need for refactoring or not by using gated recurrent unit (GRU) algorithm. The structure of the proposed approach is outlined in Figure 1. More details of the approach are given in the next subsections.

Figure 1. Proposed methodology

3.1. Datasets

In this paper, we used a public empirical dataset containing refactoring data for 7 open-source systems (antlr4, junit, mapdb, mcMMO, mct, oryx, titan) [32]. The experimental dataset used in our study is freely and publicly available at the PROMISE Repository. This makes our work easily reproducible. The dataset used in our experiments is manually validated by creating the source code metrics and the refactoring dataset for two subsequent releases of 7 well-known open-source software Java applications. The tools used to create this dataset are the RefFinder tool for identifying refactoring in the source code between two subsequent releases and the SourceMeter tool to compute source code metrics. These datasets used for empirical investigations on source code refactoring. The features include source code metrics, the refactoring types, and the relative maintainability index (RMI). There are 23 refactoring types at the class level. The dataset's characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Datasets characteristics

Dataset	No. of Attribute	Instances	No. refactoring	Percentage
antlr4	134	436	23	5.2%
junit	134	657	9	1.3%
mapdb	134	439	4	0.9%
mcMMO	134	301	3	0.99%
mct	134	2162	15	0.69%
oryx	134	536	15	2.7%
titan	134	1486	13	0.87%

In the first stage, data preprocessing in this study can be summarized as follows:

- Deletion of unnecessary features: remove the following feature (name, path, LongName, Parent, Component)
- Delete refactoring type features: 23 refactoring types at a class level have been deleted
- Replacement the summation of refactoring feature: We have modified the value of (summation of refactoring types) in each instance to binary values and encoded the summation of refactoring types "more than one" as (1) and "zero value" as (0). then use this feature as a class label.
- Sampling datasets: To improve the prediction of the minority class should be correct the imbalance problem. For that, we used the synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE). SMOTE deals with the problem of imbalanced distribution, producing new instances based on K-nearest neighbor (KNN). Computing the KNN value forms based on the similarity (we consider in this paper $K = 5$).

3.2. Gated recurrent unit algorithm

GRU model is a powerful deep learning model proposed by [33] also introduced in [34], GRU is one kind of the gated RNNs which are used to solve the common problems of gradient vanishing of traditional RNN [35]. GRU contains two gates that use it to control the information flow from the through the network. First, the gate to control the information flows into memory known as an update gate. Second, is to control the information that flows out of memory known as reset gate unlike long short-term memory (LSTM), GRU hasn't had separate memory cell, instead of that gating unit that controls the flow of information inside the unit [36].

3.4. Structural parameter selection for gated recurrent unit

To get an effective GRU model, we need to set key structural parameters, which are: 1) the number of hidden layers, 2) the number of epoch, and 3) batch size. To simplify the GRU model, we choose three hidden layers, which is a general configuration followed by [37], and we utilize for the number of the epoch from 10 until 2500. For the batch size use it between 2 to 15.

3.5. Comparisons

The last step in the proposed methodology is the comparison study, where the balanced data set and unbalanced dataset result are measured and compared.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we empirically evaluate the performance of the GRU model by using the 7 open-source software systems. We optimized GRU with three hidden layers, with a sigmoid activation function for the output layer. This study is carried out on 7 datasets that belong to different domains. The performance with the unbalanced dataset (experimental scenario 1) and with balanced datasets (experimental scenarios 2) are collected and compared in the next subsections. The performance of the GRU model is evaluated based on

accuracy, F-measure, recall, and precision. First, we conducted experiments where the dataset is unbalanced; we have evaluated the performance of the studied algorithm on 7 datasets. Then we repeat the same experiment after applying SMOTE to produce a balanced dataset. Table two summarizes the obtained Performance Results before and after applying SMOTE.

In this section, we report the comparison results of prediction performance on the balanced and unbalanced datasets. The results of scenario 2 experiment that uses the balanced dataset show better results in prediction. Our goal here is to investigate whether the balanced datasets can enhance the refactoring prediction performance using the studied deep learning algorithm on these datasets. Table 2 shows the prediction results with unbalanced data. Table 3 reveals how balancing the data can improve the prediction performance results. Most measurement results are increased noticeably, especially for recall, precision, and F-measures. In comparison between unbalanced and balanced data, the F-measure improves by at least double which is very significant.

Table 2. The results with unbalanced data

Dataset	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-measure
Antlr4	84.1	40.0	19.04	25.8
Junit	98.61	33.33	50.0	40.0
MapDB	97.8	50.0	33.3	40.0
McMMO	96.0	50.0	25.0	33.3
MCT	98.4	20.0	12.5	15.3
Titan	99.3	33.3	50.0	40.0
Oryx	97.2	20.0	50.0	28.5

Table 3. The results with balanced data

Dataset	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-measure
Antlr4	91.9	100	86.1	92.5
Junit	98.6	100	97.2	98.6
MapDB	99.3	100	98.6	99.3
McMMO	99	100	98	99
MCT	99.8	100	97.8	98.8
Titan	99.3	100	98.7	99.3
Oryx	99.3	100	98.7	99.3

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work investigates the effectiveness of using deep learning algorithms in refactoring prediction. Gated recurrent unit (GRU) algorithm is used in this study and the performance is evaluated on 7 open-source software products dataset. Moreover, balancing the data set as an enhancement preprocessing stage is addressed in this study as well. The synthetic minority over-sampling technique (SMOTE) is used for balancing the dataset. To the best of our knowledge, gated recurrent unit (GRU) algorithm is used for the first time for refactoring prediction at the class level. The algorithm shows promising performance results. The experimental results show how a balanced dataset enhances the prediction performance noticeably, where all used measures in this study are increased after using a balanced data set in the experiments. As future work, authors will try to predict the refactoring type at class or method level using a deep learning algorithm.

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